

Scientific Cruise Report

1. Cruise participants

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2. Aim of the cruise

The main aim of the cruise was to establish ecological and biogeochemical baselines in areas of the Bothnian Bay being prospected for potential seabed mining of ferromanganese (FeMn) nodules. Specifically, the cruise sought to (1) quantify benthic biodiversity across major organismal groups (bacteria, archaea, protists, meiofauna, macrofauna) within and outside the proposed mining zones; (2) measure rates of key biogeochemical processes related to carbon and nitrogen cycling, including DIC, CO₂, CH₄ fluxes, O₂ consumption, and denitrification, DNRA, and anammox; (3) collect sediments for experiments to evaluate cross-kingdom differences in recovery and the return of fluxes to baseline values following a simulated mining disturbance.

Cruise summary

The cruise *NOD2505* aboard *KBV 181* took place between 19 and 23 May 2025 in the Bothnian Bay, northern Baltic Sea. The expedition was part of the Formas-funded project on seabed mining impacts, supported by SWERVE ship time. The work aimed to establish ecological and biogeochemical baselines for areas being prospected for FeMn nodules. Sampling focused on two prospecting zones, each consisting of five sites plus one reference station, totalling twelve sites. All planned operations were completed successfully, with good weather conditions and full functionality of scientific and technical equipment.

Brief description of the daily activities

Day 1 (19 May): Mobilisation in Holmsund, safety briefing, equipment setup, and transit to the first prospecting area (Area 1). Initial CTD profiles and test deployments of the box corer were conducted.

Day 2 (20 May): Sampling at five stations in Area 1, including reference station A1_Ref. Sediment cores were collected for biodiversity and biogeochemical analyses. Van Veen grabs were used for macrofaunal sampling, and nodules were preserved for later quantification.

Day 3 (21 May): Sampling at Area 2 stations (A2_1–A2_5 and A2_Ref). Procedures followed the same protocol as in Area 1. Recolonization experiment material was collected at site A1_4 (65 cores and sediment boxes).

Day 4 (22 May): Completion of remaining sampling, on-deck sample processing, freezing, and demobilisation. Return transit to Holmsund on 23 May.

3. Scientific objectives

See above

4. Station/activities log

See above

5. Data document sheet

All sediment, water, and biological samples collected during the cruise are currently stored at Stockholm University (Department of Ecology, Environment and Plant Sciences – DEEP) under controlled temperature conditions. Samples include frozen sediment subsamples for DNA/RNA analysis, preserved meiofauna and macrofauna, and stored incubation material for biogeochemical rate measurements. Data from CTD casts, sample metadata, and laboratory results are managed under the project’s internal data policy.

After completion of analyses and publication of results, sequencing data will be deposited in the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA/SRA), and accompanying biogeochemical datasets will be archived in an open-access repository such as Zenodo or Dryad. Metadata and cruise information will be made publicly available following FAIR data principles.

Preliminary results

We have preliminary results from our experimental work. Samples collected during the cruise were used for an experimental study. The study examined the short- and long-term ecological effects of simulated seabed mining disturbances on benthic communities in the Bothnian Bay. Sediment cores collected in the cruise were used to mimic sediment removal and plume deposition, and the recovery of macrofauna, meiofauna, and bacterial communities was monitored over 48 hours, 30 days, and 120 days.

Results showed a marked decline in meiofaunal abundance (approximately 90%) and macrofaunal collapse immediately following disturbance, with little or no recovery after 120 days. Bacterial communities exhibited significant compositional shifts, characterized by reduced diversity and an increase in opportunistic taxa. In contrast, treatments simulating sediment plume deposition showed no effects over the same period. These findings provide one of the first experimental insights into multi-trophic benthic recovery after simulated seabed mining in cold, low-energy coastal systems, highlighting the vulnerability of Baltic benthos and the need for careful regulation of potential future mining operations.

Data for baseline is still being analyzed. We expect two publications to be out late 2026

